

EFFECT OF COMMUNICATION SKILLS ON GRADUATE EMPLOYMENT IN SELECTED SMALL SCALE ENTERPRISES IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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graduate employment, interpersonal skill, communication skill, selected small scale enterprises, Anambra State

Abstract: *The study examines the effect of communication skills on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria. The researcher developed two objectives such as to determine the effect of interpersonal skill on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria. Ascertain the effect of non verbal communication skill on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria. The research design used for this study is a descriptive study and the cross-sectional survey method was adopted for this study. This enabled the researcher to generate first hand data for the study and for the test of hypotheses. The sources of data for this research were mainly primary data and secondary data. From the directory of industries domiciled in the State Ministry of Commerce and Industry, and a pilot study commissioned by the researcher, 897 of this category of business was identified in the state with following breakdown for the areas being considered: Nnewi – 451; Ontisha – 476 and Awka – 243. We used Taro Yameni’s statistical formula for determining sample size from a finite population which give us 298 as the sample size. The findings of the study revealed that Interpersonal skill by the trainees have significant positive effect on graduate employment generation in Nigeria. Non verbal communication has significant positive effect on graduate employment generation in Nigeria. The study recommends that Students should be encouraged to attend industry events or community gathering, join clubs or groups, volunteer as it provides opportunities to interact with diverse individuals and practice their interpersonal skill in a supportive environment. Students should be taught communication skill to enable them make informed decisions about their finance and manage the financial risks associated with entrepreneurship.*

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1.1 Introduction

Graduates' proficiency in English language are keenly sought after by employers to help drive their organizations to compete successfully in the era of globalization and competitiveness (Hamid et al., 2014). Realizing this fact, employers of various industries actively search and screen for potential employees who are well equipped with communication skills and language proficiency so that they are able to perform better globally. Among the most sought-after skills that employers seek in potential employees is the skill of effective communication in English language. It is apparent that the proficiency to communicate effectively in the English language has been acknowledged as a key factor in getting employed since the 20th century and has a part in boosting a company's market share and performance.

All organizations rely on communication for their basic functioning. Communication is used to transfer information to their audience about the organizations' mission and vision, policies, and procedures, tasks and duties, and various activities within the company (Farmer, Slater, & Wright, 1998). As simple as communication may look, research has shown that communication can build or destroy an organization's existence. Therefore, a good communication strategy is essential for a business to survive. Communication acts as a link between decision-makers and all employees. When poorly carried out,

communication has been said to cause interpersonal conflict in organizations. What people hear or understand is largely based on experience and background. People have preconceptions about what people are going to say, and if these preconceptions do not fit into their framework of reference, adjustments are made until they do (Baskin et al., 1997).

Communication, the heart of business, is the most important of all entrepreneurial skills. An organization's ability to transmit information helps both clients and employees feel they can communicate with and ultimately trust the company. Communication is more important today than in previous years partly because the business and market conditions are more complex. The development of a strategic communication strategy and its implementation can provide a number of benefits to organizations, such as keeping employees motivated and engaged, and sharing clear, consistent messages with employees in a timely manner that in turn help with organisational productivity (Charles, 1998). Effective communication enhances organizational relationship and minimizes strikes and lockouts.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In every organization, communication serves two imperative roles. It is used by employees to disseminate the information needed and to create a sense of trust and commitment (Optum, 2015). In a workplace, communication transpired refers to exchanging information, both verbal and non-verbal communication and

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it plays an important role as it assists in the organisation work activities, avoiding missed deadlines which could affect the organisation production and growth. Good communication skills support employees to coordinate well in their tasks, within the team especially where the employees come from different parts of the society with varied cultures and background.

Poor communication skills will hamper productivity and may even cause misunderstanding within the employees. According to Karim (2016) solving people problems such as trust issues and poor communication takes up more than half of a manager's working time, so they believe that effective communication will help to cut down on the amount of management time used on resolving employee conflicts. This is tremendously important to organisations because it increases productivity and efficiency, and misunderstanding can be avoided. Communication skills present several challenges, including unclear messages, distractions, emotional barriers, and cultural differences. These can lead to misunderstandings, frustration, and damaged relationships. Effective communication relies on clear articulation, active listening, and empathy, as well as understanding the impact of cultural and emotional factors. Effective workplace communication ensures that all the organizational objectives are achieved (Ergen, 2010).

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to assess the effect of communication skills on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study focuses on achieving these objectives;

- i. To determine the effect of interpersonal skills on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- ii. To examine the effect of non-verbal communication on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Communication Skills

Communication is the process of exchanging information, ideas, thoughts, or feelings between individuals or groups through various mediums such as speech, writing, gestures, or digital platforms (Beebe, Beebe & Ivy, 2023). It involves both the transmission and the reception of messages and can occur in both formal and informal contexts. Effective communication is critical in personal, professional, and organizational settings as it helps build relationships, resolve conflicts, and enhance collaboration. Communication is where people in an organization exchange information regarding the operations of the enterprise. It is the inter-change of ideas, facts, and emotions by two or more persons by the use of words, letters, memos, and symbols.

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Communication is vital because it entails the right use of words in expressing intended ideas. Communication, according to Okute and Olom (2012), is concerned with the generation, transmission, interpretation and use of information. Klein in Ann-Marie (2015) viewed communication skills as the ability to actively listen, to communicate in oral, written, and nonverbal forms. He further reported the view of employers of labour on business education graduates that they lacked skills, including communication skills. Effective communication is another set of employability skills that are highly prized in professional service sectors (Blue, 2023; Doyle, 2022).

2.1.2 Interpersonal Skills

Interpersonal competence, or the capacity to lead others, is what a manager needs to inspire employees, resolve issues at work, and collaborate with others. The ability to lead others is known as interpersonal relation skills. It allows a manager to inspire staff, find solutions to problems at work, and work cooperatively with others. According to Fonkam (2021), a manager with interpersonal relation skills should be able to comprehend, guide, influence, and control the behaviour of the people and organisations under his supervision. Managers in interpersonal jobs must be able to inspire staff members and create and sustain positive relationships with a range of stakeholders in the business's internal and external environments (Dierdorff, Rubin, & Frederick Morgeson, 2009).

2.1.3 Non-Verbal Communication

There are two forms of language expression namely verbal and non-verbal. According to Bovee & Thill in Haryati (2001); Kristiyanti (2012), non-verbal communication is gestures, intonation of voice, attitudes and so on that will allow someone communicates without using words. Each time an interaction occurs non-verbal communication between two parties, without us realizing it will involve behavior (gesture), eye movements, changes in body posture and facial expressions. Consciously or not, these behaviors and movements are complementary to the speaking situation actually. But from another angle, this has actually created an interaction of using non-verbal language.

2.1.4 Graduate employment

Employability is seen to be a challenging term to describe. Employability has been defined in the context of UK higher education in several ways, from students “having a job” to their possessing the broad range of “knowledge, skills, and attributes” required of graduates from higher education. Early definitions of employability included “the ability of graduates to obtain a job” and relied on the straightforward test of determining if a graduate had found employment within six months of leaving HE (Dacre, Pool, and Sewell, 2007). Harvey offered “the propensity of the individual student to get employment” as a definition of employability that is similar (2001).

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Graduate employment refers to the process of graduates transitioning from academic study into paid work, encompassing the rate at which graduates find jobs and the quality of those jobs. It's a key indicator of the success of higher education in preparing students for the workforce and contributes to both individual and societal economic development. Graduate employability, a related concept, focuses on the skills, knowledge, and attributes graduates possess that make them attractive to employers (Makhene, 2022)

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Systems Theory

Because of origins from multiple disciplines, systems theory is meant to be applicable to organisms and human behaviours in different disciplines (Kast & Rosenzweig, 1972). When applied to communication, the systems theory is meant to understand the interconnectedness of the human communication and not just focus on one aspect of it (Scott, 1974). According to systems theory, components of each system are structured in a hierarchical ordering, and components are interdependent with one another in the system to the extent that one component cannot function without the support of other components. At the organizational level, the organizations and other organizations in the environment are also interdependent on one another.

The outcome of an organisation's communication has consequences on its functioning and hence it can be seen in its

overall performance. Various theories have attempted to explicate this contingency view of organization-environment relationships. The two approaches commonly cited in studying the role of organizational environments are the population ecology model (Hannan & Freeman, 1977) and the resource dependence model (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978). These two approaches converge on the importance of environments in organizational decisions and structures but diverge on the role of environmental selection. The former emphasizes the processes of how organizations are differentially selected and determined by their fitness, measured by structural forms to their environments, while the latter focuses on active, managerial processes of selection enacted by organizations in adapting themselves to the environment. In other words, selection and adaption are the two key mechanisms that can characterize these two approaches, respectively.

2.3 Empirical Review

Babatunde, Oluwafemi and Olajide, (2025) evaluated the essential employability skills of graduates in the professional services sector. Using a descriptive research design, a questionnaire was administered to 282 respondents in Lagos State. The sample size was determined using Slovin's formula and a stratified random sampling technique. Data analysis involved frequency percentage distribution, weighted mean, and analysis of variance (ANOVA). Findings reveal a significant

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proportion of respondents as team leaders, holding bachelor's degrees, and working in professional services firms with more than 151 employees. Effective communication skills emerged as the foremost requirement, complemented by leadership skills that foster enthusiasm and commitment within organizations. Notably, disparities in employability skills were found when respondents were categorized based on organizations' sizes. Concurrently, respondents reported challenges in articulating well-defined career objectives and demonstrating adaptability. These findings underscore the imperative for higher institutions to emphasize curricula that enhance graduates' employability skills, particularly in communication, leadership, critical thinking, and problem-solving. Universities should tailor their academic programs to strengthen these crucial skills, benefiting both graduates and the professional services industry. Furthermore, continuous professional development and industry-academic partnerships are recommended to keep curricula aligned with evolving industry needs, ensuring that graduates are well-equipped for the dynamic job market.

Kalpana and Kush (2025) described the efficiency of the English language classes existing in Master of Business Administration (MBA) course of various PG colleges in Marathwada region, Maharashtra. There are many MBA graduates being unemployed

because of their low self-confidence level and poor employability skills. Despite the fact that several research studies have been conducted on the importance and improvement of employability skills for postgraduate students, the challenge of those skills remains with them. This research aimed to determine the efficacy of good communication skills in MBA courses and to expose the ambiguity surrounding the low professionalism of rural students in several PG institutions. It was observed that several graduates, also in their final semester, have limited professionalism to meet campus selections with effective communication skills, which are needed to get a job at the end of their degree. Many students want to learn effective communication skills exercises in terms of developing their interpersonal skills, so innovative education systems and techniques are needed for English language faculty. As a result of the findings, the issue between English language teachers' practices, interventions, and the learners' ability requirements has been identified, as well as the need for suitable ELT (English Language Techniques) and training programs to improve speaking skills for students in rural areas.

Moses and Amakodi, (2025) investigated communication skills and employability of business education graduates in Universities in South-South, Nigeria. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 547 postgraduate students from eight Government-

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owned universities in South-South, Nigeria offering Business Education programme at the postgraduate level. 217 post graduate students were selected using the simple random sampling technique as the sample for the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-constructed questionnaire titled: Communication skills and employability of Business Education Graduates Questionnaire (CSBEGQ). The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha reliability method yielding a reliability index of 0.85. The data collected was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) coefficient method to answer research questions and test the null hypotheses. The findings of the study indicated that there is a significant relationship between communication skills and paid employment among business education graduates and there is a significant relationship between communication skills and self-employment among business education graduates in South-South, Nigeria.

Akinbode and Oyelude, (2020) investigated the deficits of 21st century skills among fresh graduates in Nigeria and their increased level of unemployment and underemployment. The objective of the study was achieved through the survey of human resource practitioners in Nigeria. Data collected were analysed with both descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings revealed that a significant proportion of Nigerian fresh graduates were deficient in 21st century skills and this has contributed

significantly to their underemployment and unemployment over the years. The study concludes that for fresh graduates' in Nigeria to be employable, they should acquire 21st century skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, creativity and innovation, local and global connections, and information communication and technology. It was recommended that tertiary educational institutions and government should as a matter of urgency review teaching curricula and encourages the development of lecturers to address the human resource needs of industries in the 21st century and beyond.

Isai, et al. (2019) investigated the importance of communication skills for employment and by adopting theory of communication, it wishes to address in detail employer's expectations. Five fresh graduates from local and private universities and two human resource officers (H R) from one organisation participated in this study. A semi-structured questionnaire was utilized as a tool to collect the data. The findings show that a majority of fresh graduates were weak in communication skills in relation to clarity, completeness, conciseness, and correctness. The inaccurate vocabulary (clarity), incomplete sentences (conciseness), unable to provide detailed answers (completeness), and error in grammar in the utterances and sentences (correctness) were found in the communication skills by these graduates. The study suggests the integration of 4Cs (clarity, conciseness, completeness and correctness) into

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the current communication skills course modules, facilitation of simulated interviews to assist undergraduates enhance their communication skills prior to attending any actual job interviews.

Methodology

The design considered appropriate for this study is descriptive survey design. The study was in Anambra State, particularly the areas in the State with cluster of industries. The area as like Onitsha, Nnewi, Awka and their environs would be covered in the study. The data to be collected for the study would be principally primary to be complemented with secondary data. From the directory of industries domiciled in the State Ministry of Commerce and Industry, and a pilot study commissioned by the researcher, 897 of this category of business was identified in the state with following breakdown for the areas being considered: Nnewi – 451; Ontisha – 476 and Awka – 243. We used Taro Yameni's statistical formula for determining sample size from a finite population which give us 298 as the sample size. An item structured instrument designed to reflect the modified five (5) points Likert scale of strongly agreed, agree, disagree, strongly disagree and undecided by the researcher, would be used to elicit

information from the respondents on wide range of issues bordering on entrepreneurial skills acquisition and employment generation for the graduates in Nigeria. Pearson Correlation and multiple regression analysis would be used in verifying the claims of the various null hypotheses. All tests will be carried out at 0.05 level of significance. This being the probability level at which are would be willing to risk type I error which is the error of rejecting the null when it is in fact true.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.0 Introduction

This chapter deals with the presentation and analysis of data collected from the population under study through questionnaires and interview. 298 copies of the same questionnaire were distributed, out of which 288 copies were returned and out the returned copies, 10 copies were not properly filled, while 7 copies were spoilt. So the percentages of returned copies is 83%, unreturned copies 3%, spoilt copies 1% and the 271 number of questionnaire used which for the analysis was 84%.The analysis is based on frequency distribution and simple percentages.

Table 4.1: Gender of the Respondents

S/N	Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	Male	173	63.7	64.7	63.7
2.	Female	98	36.3	36.3	100.0
	Total	271	100.0	100.0	-

Source: Field Survey, 2025

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From Table 4.1, it could be seen that male respondents are 173 and it represents 63.7 percent of the sample while their female counterparts are 98, representing also 36.3 percent of the total. The implication is that there

are more males than females in the sample. It also shows that there are more males in the operation of small businesses than females in Nigeria.

Table 4.2 Age Bracket of the Respondents

S/N	Age Bracket (in years)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	18 – 27	24	9.1	9.1	9.1
2.	28 – 37	56	20.5	20.5	29.6
3.	38 – 47	97	35.7	35.7	65.3
4.	48 – 57	53	19.4	19.4	84.7
5.	58 and above	41	15.3	15.3	100.0
Total		271	100.0	100.0	-

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2 shows that age bracket of 38 to 47 years has the highest number of 97 operators of small business representing 35.7 percent of the sample. It implies that small scale businesses in the state are dominated by young people who

perhaps are graduates of tertiary institutions. The study is focused on how the business environment can be improved to attract more people in the sector so that unemployment can be significantly impacted.

Table 4.3: Educational Attainment of the Respondents

S/N	Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	High Sch. Cert.	45	16.6	16.6	16.6
2.	NCE/OND	63	23.2	23.2	39.8
3.	HND/First Degree	110	40.6	40.6	80.4
4.	Professional Cert.	37	13.7	13.7	94.1
5.	Higher degrees	16	5.9	5.9	100.0
Total		271	100.0	100.0	-

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis of respondents' educational background showed that 110 of them representing 40.6 percent of the sample have qualifications ranging from Higher National

Diploma (HND) to First degree. Sixty-three of them representing 23.2 percent have either National certificate of Education (NCE) or Ordinary National Diploma (OND) while 37 of them representing 13.7 percent have

professional certificate. The implication of the results is that the sample consists of

respondents who are fairly literature.

Table 4.4: Length of Time in the Industry

S/N	Organizational Tenure	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	Below 5 years	59	21.8	21.8	21.8
2.	5 to 10 years	67	24.7	24.7	46.5
3.	11 to 15 years	95	35.0	35.0	81.5
4.	16 and above years	50	18.5	18.5	100.0
	Total	271	100.0	100.0	-

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.4 shows that 59 respondents representing 21.8 percent of the sample have operated in their respective industries for less than five years, 67 of them representing 24.7 percent have been in business for upward of 5 to 10 years, 95 of them representing about 35 percent have had organizational experience between 11 to 15 years while 50 respondents representing 18.5 percent of the sample have operated for 16 years and above. The result of the analysis of the organizational tenure coupled with their educational attainment showed that the respondents have what it takes to effectively engage in a discussion concerning entrepreneurship skills acquisition and graduate employment generation.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

In this section of the analysis, all hypotheses formulated to guide the objectives as well as strengthen the analysis were tested through the application of multiple regression analysis. The

tests were basically conducted to verify the claims of the various null hypotheses. The hypotheses were mainly on the effects of the independent variables on graduate employment generation.

Table 4.10: Correlation Analysis

Correlation Matrix

** Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Variables		Graduate Employment Generation	Interpersonal Skills	Communication skills
Graduate Employment Generation	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1	.527**	-.511**
	N	271	271	271
Interpersonal Skills	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.527**	1	.530**
	N	271	271	271
Non verbal	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.511**	.530**	1
	N	271	271	271

* Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.10 presents the correlation matrix of the dependent and independent variables. The correlation result showed mainly positive relationship between the dependent and independent variable similarly, the

relationships were significant more at 0.05 level of significance than they were at 0.01 level. The results had no issue of multicollinearity or orthogonal relationships. In other words, the result is good enough for multiple regression analysis to be performed on them.

Table 4.11: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

ANOVA^b

Source of Variation	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-ratio	Sig.
Regression	4	225.309	56.327	13.732	.000 ^a
Residual	95	389.725	4.102		
Total	99	615.034			

a. Predictor: (constant), relevant interpersonal skill, and non verbal communication skills.

b. Dependent variable: Graduate Employment Generation

The analysis of variance result presented in Table 4.11 with an F-Statistic of 13.732 shows

Table 4.12: Summary of Regression Results

Model	R	R.Square	Adjusted R-Square	Standard Error of the Estimate	Durbin Watson
I	0.527	0.504	0.497	0.38256	2.0105

a. Predictor: (constant), relevant interpersonal skill, and non verbal communication skills.

Table 4.12 is the presentation of the multiple regression results. The table showed that regression coefficient represented by 'R' with a value of 0.527 implies that 52.7 percent relationship exists between the dependent and

that the model is statistically significant and therefore, it is fit and valid for predictions because the probability level ($P_{0.000}$) is less than $P \leq 0.05$.

independent variables. Similarly, the coefficient of determination represented by 'R²' with a value of 0.504 shows that 50.4 percent variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables. Therefore, the explanatory power of the model is 50.4 percent.

Table 4.13: Coefficients of the Predictor Variables, t-values and the Sig. Level

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sign
	β	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-.174	.205	-	-.756	.446
interpersonal skill	.627	.048	.525	10.323	.000
Non verbal communication skills	.491	.071	-.481	3.506	.003

a. Dependent Variable: Graduate Employment Generation

As could be seen from Table 4.13 which presents the coefficients of the variables, t-values and the significance level, some variables have high coefficients thus indicating their relevance in the model. The high coefficients represents the level of influence such independents variables have on graduate employment generation as the dependent variable. The results show equally the conformity of the expected signs, the a priori of the coefficients of the independent variables.

Re-Statement of the Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated to guide and strengthen the analysis in the study were re-stated and tested in this section of the analysis through the aid of the results of the multiple regression analysis presented in Table 4.13. Accordingly, the null and alternative hypotheses were stated as follows:

Hypothesis one

Ho: Interpersonal skill do not have a significant effect on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria...

H₁: Interpersonal skill have a significant effect on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Non verbal Communication skills do not have a significant effect on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

H₁: Non verbal Communication skill have a significant effect on graduate employment in

selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Interpretation of Regression Results

From Table 4.13, the coefficient of interpersonal skills represented by α_1 has a value of 0.525 and it means that when the interpersonal skill is raised by one unit, graduate employment generation will be increased by 52.5 percent if other variables in the model are held constant. The t-value (10.323) and the significant level (0.000) corresponding to the coefficient showed that the coefficient is significant because 0.000 is less than 0.05. Consequently, the null hypotheses was rejected while the alternative which suggests that acquisition of interpersonal skill has a significant positive effect on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria was accepted.

Finally, the coefficient of non verbal communication skill is represented in the model by α_4 and it has a value of -0.481. It means that when the coefficient is increased by one unit, graduate employment generation opportunities will decrease by 48.1 percent. The t-value of 3.506 and the corresponding significance level of 0.003 are indications that the coefficient is significant but with negative effect because 0.003 is less than 0.05. Consequently, we accepted the null hypothesis and conclude that non verbal has a significant positive effect on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Conclusion and recommendation

The result of the first test of hypothesis in this study suggests that the interpersonal skill has a significant positive effect on graduate employment in selected small scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria. The result is consistent with that of Ekeruche and Echedom (2023) in their study interpersonal skills as correlate of career development of librarians in academic libraries in South - South, Nigeria. Their study revealed among others that; there is a high positive relationship between interpersonal skills of librarians and their career development in academic libraries, and there exist a significant relationship between interpersonal skills of librarians and their career development in academic libraries. Oyadiran, lawal and Otu (2022) in their study on the impact of interpersonal relationship on organizational performance revealed that interpersonal relationship skills such as conflict management skills, communication skills, positive attitude, good leadership skills and team work play significant role in improving organizational performance.

The result of the second test of hypothesis showed that non verbal communication skill has a significant positive effect on graduate employment. The result is in line with that of Naisujaki and jafari (2023) in their study on assessment of communication skill attributes for technical and vocational education training (TVET) graduates required by employers in Tanzania. Their study established that

employers require graduates who have ability to build a team and work in a team, ask for an apology when feeling guilty, write clearly, concise and correct manner, prepare and deliver an oral presentation, conduct meetings and minute writing, negotiate with the clients/customers and express ideas, thoughts and feelings effectively in writing and in speech. Moses and Amakodi (2025) in their study on communication skills and employability of business education graduates in Universities in South-South, Nigeria found out that there is a significant relationship between communication skills and paid employment among business education graduates and there is a significant relationship between communication skills and self-employment among business education graduates in South-South, Nigeria.

Recommendation

1. Students should be encouraged to attend industry events or community gathering, join clubs or groups, volunteer as it provides opportunities to interact with diverse individuals and practice their interpersonal skill in a supportive environment.
2. Students should be engaged in activities such as volunteering, group discussions, mock interview, explore online resources (TED talks and workshop) to learn about effective communication techniques to practice in real word settings.

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